

Supplemental Material

Microscale hydrodynamic cloaking and shielding via electro-osmosis

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S.1. GOVERNING EQUATIONS FOR NON-UNIFORM ELECTRO-OSMOTIC FLOW IN A HELE-SHAW CONFIGURATION

We consider the creeping flow of a viscous fluid of density $\tilde{\rho}$, viscosity $\tilde{\mu}$, and dielectric permittivity $\tilde{\epsilon}$ within a narrow gap \tilde{h} between two parallel plates forming a Hele-Shaw configuration. We denote dimensional variables by tildes, non-dimensional variables without tildes and characteristic values by an asterisk superscript.

We employ a Cartesian coordinate system $(\tilde{x}, \tilde{y}, \tilde{z})$, where the \tilde{x} and \tilde{y} axes lie at the lower plane and the \tilde{z} axis is perpendicular thereto. We adopt the \parallel subscript to denote directions within the $\tilde{x} - \tilde{y}$ plane, and the \perp subscript for the perpendicular \tilde{z} direction. In the following, these directions are referred to as “longitudinal” and “transverse”. The lower and upper plates have an arbitrary zeta-potential distribution, defined as $\tilde{\zeta}^L(\tilde{x}, \tilde{y})$ and $\tilde{\zeta}^U(\tilde{x}, \tilde{y})$, respectively, which vary over a characteristic length scale \tilde{r}_0 in the $\tilde{x} - \tilde{y}$ plane. An electrostatic in-plane electric field $\tilde{\mathbf{E}}_{\parallel}$ is applied parallel to the plates.

The fluid velocity $\tilde{\mathbf{u}} = (\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{\parallel}, \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{\perp}) = (\tilde{u}, \tilde{v}, \tilde{w})$ and pressure distribution \tilde{p} are induced either due to an externally applied pressure-driven flow or due to an electro-osmotic flow resulting from the interaction of the applied electric field with the zeta potential on the walls.

In typical microfluidic configurations, electrokinetic effects are confined to a small length scale in the vicinity of the charged surface, called the electric-double layer (thickness: ~ 10 nm). Usually, its thickness is much smaller than all other relevant length scales [1, 2]. In this thin-electric-double layer regime [3, 4], the fluid motion in the bulk is governed by the continuity and momentum equations

$$\tilde{\nabla} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{u}} = 0, \quad \tilde{\rho} \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{u}}}{\partial \tilde{t}} + \tilde{\mathbf{u}} \cdot \tilde{\nabla} \tilde{\mathbf{u}} \right) = -\tilde{\nabla} \tilde{p} + \tilde{\mu} \tilde{\nabla}^2 \tilde{\mathbf{u}}, \quad (\text{S1})$$

and the electro-osmotic effects are incorporated through the use of the Helmholtz–Smoluchowski slip boundary conditions [2],

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{\parallel}|_{\tilde{z}=0} = -\frac{\tilde{\epsilon} \tilde{\zeta}^L \tilde{\mathbf{E}}_{\parallel}}{\tilde{\mu}}, \quad \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{\parallel}|_{\tilde{z}=\tilde{h}} = -\frac{\tilde{\epsilon} \tilde{\zeta}^U \tilde{\mathbf{E}}_{\parallel}}{\tilde{\mu}}, \quad (\text{S2})$$

where \tilde{t} is time.

By making use of the Helmholtz–Smoluchowski slip condition, we have implicitly assumed that surface conduction is negligible and thus consider asymptotically small Dukhin numbers (see [1]),

$$Du = \frac{\tilde{\sigma}_s}{\tilde{\sigma}_b \tilde{h}} \ll 1, \quad (\text{S3})$$

where $\tilde{\sigma}_s/\tilde{\sigma}_b$ is the ratio of surface and bulk conductivities. This ratio defines a length scale which determines the spatial variations of the electric field due to the non-uniformity in surface conduction [5]. For high Dukhin numbers, surface conduction becomes apparent, resulting in significant spatial variations in the electric field and in bulk concentration gradients, which may lead to chemiosmotic flow effects [6, 7]. In the limit of $Du \ll 1$ and thin electric-double layers, the fluid in the bulk is electrically neutral and the electric field $\tilde{\mathbf{E}}_{\parallel}$ is solenoidal, i.e., $\tilde{\nabla} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{E}}_{\parallel} = 0$. The electric field can be expressed through an electrostatic potential $\tilde{\varphi}$, $\tilde{\mathbf{E}}_{\parallel} = -\tilde{\nabla} \tilde{\varphi}$, that is governed by the Laplace equation

$$\tilde{\nabla}^2 \tilde{\varphi} = 0, \quad (\text{S4})$$

which satisfies the insulation boundary conditions on the walls, $\partial \tilde{\varphi} / \partial \tilde{z}|_{\tilde{z}=0, \tilde{h}} = 0$. The latter is appropriate in situations where either the dielectric permittivity or the conductivity of the fluid between the plates is much higher than that of the wall material.

The characteristic value of the velocity in the $\tilde{x} - \tilde{y}$ plane, \tilde{u}^* , is set by the Helmholtz–Smoluchowski slip condition as $\tilde{u}^* = -\tilde{\epsilon} \tilde{\zeta}^* \tilde{E}^* / \tilde{\mu}$, where $\tilde{\zeta}^*$ and \tilde{E}^* are the characteristic values of the zeta potential and the externally applied electric field, respectively. The characteristic time scale is $\tilde{t}^* = \tilde{r}_0 / \tilde{u}^*$, whereas the characteristic velocity in the \tilde{z} direction, \tilde{w}^* , and the characteristic pressure, \tilde{p}^* , remain to be determined from scaling arguments. Scaling by the characteristic dimensions, we introduce the following normalized quantities: $(x, y, z) = (\tilde{x}/\tilde{r}_0, \tilde{y}/\tilde{r}_0, \tilde{z}/\tilde{h})$, $t = \tilde{t}/\tilde{t}^*$, $(u, v, w) = (\tilde{u}/\tilde{u}^*, \tilde{v}/\tilde{u}^*, \tilde{w}/\tilde{w}^*)$, $p = \tilde{p}/\tilde{p}^*$, $\zeta = \tilde{\zeta}/\tilde{\zeta}^*$, $\mathbf{E}_{\parallel} = \tilde{\mathbf{E}}_{\parallel}/\tilde{E}^*$ and $\varphi = \tilde{\varphi}/(\tilde{E}^* \tilde{r}_0)$.

In microscale flows, fluidic inertia is commonly negligible compared to viscous stresses. Further, the transverse scale is typically much smaller than the longitudinal scale. Therefore, we restrict our analysis to shallow geometries and neglect fluidic inertia, represented by a small reduced Reynolds number,

$$\epsilon = \frac{\tilde{h}}{\tilde{r}_0} \ll 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \epsilon Re = \epsilon \frac{\tilde{\rho} \tilde{u}^* \tilde{h}}{\tilde{\mu}} \ll 1, \quad (\text{S5})$$

and from order-of-magnitude analysis of the continuity and momentum equations (S1) obtain the expressions for the characteristic vertical velocity, $\tilde{w}^* = \epsilon \tilde{u}^*$, and the pressure scale, $\tilde{p}^* = \tilde{\mu} \tilde{u}^* \tilde{r}_0 / \tilde{h}^2 = -\tilde{\epsilon} \tilde{\zeta}^* \tilde{E}^* \tilde{r}_0 / \tilde{h}^2$. Substituting these results into (S1)–(S4), and then expanding the velocity and pressure in powers of ϵ and considering the leading order, $O(\epsilon^0)$, results in the lubrication equations, expressed here by the following set of normalized equations and boundary conditions [8],

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} = 0, \quad (\text{S6})$$

$$\nabla_{\parallel} p = \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{u}_{\parallel}}{\partial z^2}, \quad (\text{S7})$$

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial z} = 0, \quad (\text{S8})$$

$$\nabla_{\parallel}^2 \varphi = 0, \quad (\text{S9})$$

$$\frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial z} = 0, \quad (\text{S10})$$

$$\mathbf{u}_{\parallel}|_{z=0} = -\zeta^L \nabla_{\parallel} \varphi, \quad \mathbf{u}_{\parallel}|_{z=1} = -\zeta^U \nabla_{\parallel} \varphi \quad \text{and} \quad u_{\perp}|_{z=0,1} = 0, \quad (\text{S11})$$

where $\nabla_{\parallel} = (\partial/\partial x, \partial/\partial y)$ is the two-dimensional gradient and from (S8) and (S10), it follows that $p = p(x, y)$ and $\varphi = \varphi(x, y)$, i.e. the pressure and electric potential are independent of z to leading order, consistent with the lubrication approximation.

Integrating the in-plane momentum equation (S7) twice with respect to z and using the slip boundary conditions (S11) yields the in-plane velocity field, which is then averaged over z leading to the depth-averaged in-plane velocity

$$\langle \mathbf{u}_{\parallel} \rangle = -\frac{1}{12} \nabla_{\parallel} p - \langle \zeta \rangle \nabla_{\parallel} \varphi. \quad (\text{S12})$$

where $\langle \zeta \rangle$ is the arithmetic mean value of the zeta potential on the walls, $\langle \zeta \rangle = (\zeta^U + \zeta^L)/2$. Similarly, integrating the continuity equation (S6) over the channel height and using the no-penetration boundary conditions yields

$$\nabla_{\parallel} \cdot \langle \mathbf{u}_{\parallel} \rangle = 0. \quad (\text{S13})$$

Applying the two-dimensional divergence to (S12) and using (S13), we obtain an equation in terms of the pressure only,

$$\nabla_{\parallel}^2 p = -12 \nabla_{\parallel} \langle \zeta \rangle \cdot \nabla_{\parallel} \varphi. \quad (\text{S14})$$

Similarly, applying the normal component of the curl operator to (S12) and using $(\nabla_{\parallel} \times \langle \mathbf{u}_{\parallel} \rangle) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{z}} = -\nabla_{\parallel}^2 \psi$, leads to an equation for the depth-averaged stream function $\psi(x, y)$,

$$\nabla_{\parallel}^2 \psi = (\nabla_{\parallel} \langle \zeta \rangle \times \nabla_{\parallel} \varphi) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{z}}, \quad (\text{S15})$$

which is related to the velocity field through $\langle \mathbf{u}_{\parallel} \rangle = (\partial\psi/\partial y, -\partial\psi/\partial x)$.

Equations (S14) and (S15) are a set of uncoupled Poisson equations describing the pressure and flow fields resulting from non-uniform EOF. These equations depend on the electric field distribution and thus require the solution of the uncoupled electrostatic problem (S9) and (S10).

S.2. THEORY FOR HYDRODYNAMIC SHIELDING AND CLOAKING USING NON-UNIFORM ELECTRO-OSMOTIC FLOW

Here, we present a detailed derivation of the theoretical approach for shielding and cloaking objects inside microchannels using non-uniform electro-osmotic flow. We refer to **shielding** as to the elimination of hydrodynamic force acting on the object and **cloaking** as to the hiding an object hydrodynamically such that an external flow is "unaware" of the presence of the object.

We consider a pillar-shaped object with arbitrary cross-sectional shape confined between the walls of a Hele-Shaw cell and subjected to a pressure-driven flow with an externally imposed mean velocity u_{ext} along the x -axis, as shown in Fig. S1. To enable analytical treatment, we specifically focus on an object with the shape of a slightly deformed cylinder, parameterized by

$$r_{\text{obj}} = 1 + \beta f(\theta), \quad (\text{S16})$$

where $|\beta| \ll 1$ is a small parameter representing the geometrical deviations from a perfect circular shape, and $f(\theta)$ is an arbitrary smooth function, normalized such that the maximum of its absolute value is unity, $\max(|f|) = 1$. The corresponding normal and tangential unit vectors of the parameterization (S16) are

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}}_{\text{obj}} = \hat{\mathbf{r}} - \beta \frac{df(\theta)}{d\theta} \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} + O(\beta^2), \quad \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{\text{obj}} = \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} + \beta \frac{df(\theta)}{d\theta} \hat{\mathbf{r}} + O(\beta^2). \quad (\text{S17})$$

FIG. S1. Schematic illustration of the examined configuration, showing the relevant physical and geometric parameters. (a) We consider an object with the shape of a slightly deformed cylinder confined between the two parallel plates of a Hele-Shaw cell, subjected to pressure-driven flow due to externally imposed mean velocity \tilde{u}_{ext} along the \tilde{x} -axis. The plates are separated by a small gap \hat{h} and are functionalized with a uniform zeta potential $\tilde{\zeta}_0$ within a region with the shape of a slightly circle to establish non-uniform electro-osmotic flow upon application of the electric field \tilde{E} . The electro-osmotic flow can be tuned either for cloaking or shielding of the object. (b) Applying the lubrication approximation, we average over the depth of the cell and reduce the analysis to a two-dimensional problem, in which \tilde{r}_{obj} and $\tilde{r}_{\text{cl,sh}}$ are parameterizations of the object and the cloaking/shielding region, respectively.

To cloak and shield the object hydrodynamically, we also consider a region with the shape of a slightly deformed circle, parameterized by

$$r_{\text{cl,sh}} = r_a + \beta g(\theta). \quad (\text{S18})$$

This region surrounds the object, i.e. $r_{\text{cl}} > r_{\text{obj}}$, with the corresponding normal and tangential unit vectors

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}}_{\text{cl,sh}} = \hat{\mathbf{r}} - \frac{\beta}{r_a} \frac{dg(\theta)}{d\theta} \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} + O(\beta^2), \quad \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{\text{cl,sh}} = \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} + \frac{\beta}{r_a} \frac{dg(\theta)}{d\theta} \hat{\mathbf{r}} + O(\beta^2). \quad (\text{S19})$$

We examine configurations where the lower and upper plates acquire a spatially uniform zeta potential ζ_0 within a cloaking/shielding region (S18),

$$\langle \zeta \rangle = \zeta^U = \zeta^L = \begin{cases} \zeta_0 & r_{\text{obj}} \leq r < r_{\text{cl,sh}} \\ 0 & r > r_{\text{cl,sh}} \end{cases}. \quad (\text{S20})$$

we assume that the pillar-shaped object acquires the same zeta potential ζ_0 at its surface.

Upon application of an electric field along the x -axis, which approaches a constant value E far from the object, non-uniform electro-osmotic flow is established in addition to pressure-driven flow according to (S12)

$$\langle \mathbf{u}_{\parallel} \rangle = -\frac{1}{12} \nabla_{\parallel} p + \mathbf{u}_{\text{slip}}, \quad (\text{S21})$$

where \mathbf{u}_{slip} is the electro-osmotic slip velocity in the cloaking/shielding region,

$$\mathbf{u}_{\text{slip}} = \begin{cases} -\langle \zeta \rangle \nabla_{\parallel} \varphi & r_{\text{obj}} \leq r < r_{\text{cl,sh}} \\ 0 & r > r_{\text{cl,sh}} \end{cases}. \quad (\text{S22})$$

As we show below, the established non-uniform electro-osmotic flow can be tuned either to eliminate pressure gradients in the shielding region, resulting in a reduction of the hydrodynamic force on the object, or to hide the object, such that the flow outside is “unaware” of the presence of the object. We emphasize that while the object shape $f(\theta)$ is prescribed, the shape of the cloaking/shielding region $g(\theta)$ is *a priori* unknown. In the next sections, we use the governing equations (S9), (S14) and (S21) to determine $g(\theta)$ and the relation between the magnitudes of pressure-driven and electro-osmotic flows required for cloaking and shielding. Note that depending on whether the goal is cloaking or shielding, we will obtain different relations between the flow magnitudes and different functions $g(\theta)$. These equations are supplemented by the following boundary conditions

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}}_{\text{obj}} \cdot \nabla_{\parallel} \varphi = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{\mathbf{n}}_{\text{obj}} \cdot \nabla_{\parallel} p = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad r = r_{\text{obj}}, \quad (\text{S23})$$

$$\varphi = -Er \cos \theta \quad \text{and} \quad p = -12u_{\text{ext}} r \cos \theta \quad \text{as} \quad r \rightarrow \infty, \quad (\text{S24})$$

$$p_{in} = p_{out} \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{\mathbf{n}}_{\text{cl, sh}} \cdot \langle \mathbf{u}_{\parallel} \rangle_{in} = \hat{\mathbf{n}}_{\text{cl, sh}} \cdot \langle \mathbf{u}_{\parallel} \rangle_{out} \quad \text{at} \quad r = r_{\text{cl, sh}}, \quad (\text{S25})$$

where the subscripts *in* and *out* correspond to the pressure and flow fields within ($r_{\text{obj}} < r < r_{\text{cl, sh}}$) and outside the cloaking/shielding region ($r > r_{\text{cl, sh}}$). The first two conditions (S23) correspond to no-penetration and insulation at the object surface, whereas the next two conditions (S24) correspond to a uniform externally applied velocity and an electric field along x -axis far from the object. The last boundary conditions (S25) are matching conditions, corresponding to the continuity of the pressure and normal velocity at $r = r_{\text{cl, sh}}$.

Since the electrostatic problem can be solved independently from the hydrodynamic one, we start with the derivation of the expression for the electric potential.

S.2.1. Electrostatic potential

Here, we solve (S10) together with the corresponding boundary conditions (S23)–(S24) and obtain a solution for the electrostatic potential around a slightly deformed cylinder employing a boundary perturbation method. We consider the solution as a regular perturbation about a circular shape, defining the asymptotic expansion

$$\varphi = \varphi^{(0)} + \beta\varphi^{(1)} + O(\beta^2), \quad (\text{S26})$$

and find that the solution for $\varphi^{(i)}$ ($i = 0, 1$) satisfies the Laplace equation (S9) at each order. To evaluate $\nabla_{\parallel}\varphi|_{r=r_{\text{obj}}}$, appearing in the boundary condition (S23), we expand $\nabla_{\parallel}\varphi$ around $r = 1$ and use (S26) to obtain

$$\nabla_{\parallel}\varphi|_{r=r_{\text{obj}}} = \nabla_{\parallel}\varphi^{(0)}|_{r=1} + \beta\nabla_{\parallel}\varphi^{(1)}|_{r=1} + \beta f(\theta) \frac{\partial \nabla_{\parallel}\varphi^{(0)}}{\partial r}|_{r=1} + O(\beta^2). \quad (\text{S27})$$

Using (S26) and (S27), the boundary conditions (S23)–(S24) at the leading and the first order take the form

$$\frac{\partial \varphi^{(0)}}{\partial r}|_{r=1} = 0, \quad \varphi^{(0)}|_{r \rightarrow \infty} = -Er \cos \theta, \quad (\text{S28})$$

$$\frac{\partial \varphi^{(1)}}{\partial r}|_{r=1} = \frac{df(\theta)}{d\theta} \frac{\partial \varphi^{(0)}}{\partial \theta}|_{r=1} - f(\theta) \frac{\partial^2 \varphi^{(0)}}{\partial r^2}|_{r=1}, \quad \varphi^{(1)}|_{r \rightarrow \infty} = 0. \quad (\text{S29})$$

The leading-order solution then reads

$$\varphi^{(0)}(r, \theta) = -Er \left(1 + \frac{1}{r^2} \right) \cos \theta. \quad (\text{S30})$$

Using (S30), the boundary condition at the surface of the object at the first order is obtained as

$$\frac{\partial \varphi^{(1)}}{\partial r}|_{r=1} = 2E \left[f(\theta) \cos \theta + \frac{df(\theta)}{d\theta} \sin \theta \right]. \quad (\text{S31})$$

The general solution of the Laplace equation in polar coordinates for a decaying electric potential is

$$\varphi^{(1)}(r, \theta) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} r^{-n} [C_n^1 \cos(n\theta) + C_n^2 \sin(n\theta)]. \quad (\text{S32})$$

To determine the coefficients C_n^1 and C_n^2 , we first write $f(\theta)$ as a Fourier series expansion

$$f(\theta) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} [a_n \cos(n\theta) + b_n \sin(n\theta)], \quad (\text{S33})$$

where the coefficients a_n and b_n are defined as

$$a_0 = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(t) dt, \quad a_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(t) \cos(nt) dt, \quad b_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(t) \sin(nt) dt, \quad n = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (\text{S34})$$

Substituting (S32) and (S33) into (S31), leads to

$$-\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n [C_n^1 \cos(n\theta) + C_n^2 \sin(n\theta)] = 2E \left[\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a_n [\cos(n\theta) \cos\theta - n \sin(n\theta) \sin\theta] + b_n [\sin(n\theta) \cos\theta + n \cos(n\theta) \sin\theta] \right]. \quad (\text{S35})$$

Using elementary properties of trigonometric functions, the right-hand side of (S35) can be rewritten as

$$2 \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n [\cos(n\theta) \cos\theta - n \sin(n\theta) \sin\theta] + b_n [\sin(n\theta) \cos\theta + n \cos(n\theta) \sin\theta] \right] \\ = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n [(n+1) \cos((n+1)\theta) - (n-1) \cos((n-1)\theta)] + b_n [(n+1) \sin((n+1)\theta) - (n-1) \sin((n-1)\theta)], \quad (\text{S36})$$

so that (S35) takes the form

$$-\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n [C_n^1 \cos(n\theta) + C_n^2 \sin(n\theta)] = E \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n [(n+1) \cos((n+1)\theta) - (n-1) \cos((n-1)\theta)] \right] \\ + E \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} b_n [(n+1) \sin((n+1)\theta) - (n-1) \sin((n-1)\theta)] \right]. \quad (\text{S37})$$

Next, we employ the orthogonality relations of trigonometric functions, given by $\int_0^{2\pi} \sin(n\theta) \cos(m\theta) d\theta = 0$ and

$$\int_0^{2\pi} \cos(n\theta) \cos(m\theta) d\theta = \begin{cases} 2\pi & m = n = 0 \\ \pi & m = n \neq 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad \int_0^{2\pi} \sin(n\theta) \sin(m\theta) d\theta = \begin{cases} \pi & m = n \neq 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}. \quad (\text{S38})$$

When multiplying both sides of (S37) by $\cos(j\theta)$ and integrating with respect to θ from 0 to 2π , while making use of (S38), we obtain an expression for C_n^1 . Similarly, multiplying (S37) by $\sin(j\theta)$ and integrating provides an expression for C_n^2 . The resulting expressions for C_n^1 and C_n^2 are

$$C_n^1 = E [a_{n+1} - a_{n-1}], \quad C_n^2 = E [b_{n+1} - b_{n-1}], \quad (\text{S39})$$

and thus the first-order solution for the electrostatic potential is given by

$$\varphi^{(1)}(r, \theta) = E \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} r^{-n} [(a_{n+1} - a_{n-1}) \cos(n\theta) + (b_{n+1} - b_{n-1}) \sin(n\theta)]. \quad (\text{S40})$$

S.2.2. Pressure and flow fields

In this section, we solve (S14) with the corresponding boundary conditions (S23)–(S25) using (S30) and (S40) and obtain solutions for the pressure and flow field. Similarly to (S26), we consider the pressure and flow field as regular perturbations about a circular shape, defining the asymptotic expansions

$$p = p^{(0)} + \beta p^{(1)} + O(\beta^2), \quad (\text{S41})$$

and

$$\langle \mathbf{u}_{\parallel} \rangle = \langle \mathbf{u}_{\parallel} \rangle^{(0)} + \beta \langle \mathbf{u}_{\parallel} \rangle^{(1)} + O(\beta^2). \quad (\text{S42})$$

We also expand the electro-osmotic slip velocity \mathbf{u}_{slip} in the cloaking/shielding region as

$$\mathbf{u}_{\text{slip}} = \mathbf{u}_{\text{slip}}^{(0)} + \beta \mathbf{u}_{\text{slip}}^{(1)} + O(\beta^2). \quad (\text{S43})$$

Using (S22), (S30), (S40) and (S43), we obtain the following explicit expressions for $\mathbf{u}_{\text{slip}}^{(0)} = u_{r, \text{slip}}^{(0)} \hat{\mathbf{r}} + u_{\theta, \text{slip}}^{(0)} \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ and $\mathbf{u}_{\text{slip}}^{(1)} = u_{r, \text{slip}}^{(1)} \hat{\mathbf{r}} + u_{\theta, \text{slip}}^{(1)} \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$

$$\mathbf{u}_{\text{slip}}^{(0)} = u_{\text{EOF}} \left[\left(1 - \frac{1}{r^2} \right) \cos\theta \hat{\mathbf{r}} - \left(1 + \frac{1}{r^2} \right) \sin\theta \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \right], \quad (\text{S44})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}_{\text{slip}}^{(1)} &= u_{\text{EOF}} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} r^{-1-n} n [(a_{n+1} - a_{n-1}) \cos(n\theta) + (b_{n+1} - b_{n-1}) \sin(n\theta)] \hat{\mathbf{r}} \\ &+ u_{\text{EOF}} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} r^{-1-n} [(a_{n+1} - a_{n-1}) \sin(n\theta) - (b_{n+1} - b_{n-1}) \cos(n\theta)] \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S45})$$

where u_{EOF} is defined as

$$\overline{u_{\text{EOF}}} = \langle \zeta \rangle E = \zeta_0 E. \quad (\text{S46})$$

Substituting (S41) into (S14) and using (S20), we find that the pressure satisfies the Laplace equation within and outside the cloaking/shielding region at each order in β . Using (S21) and (S23)–(S25), the boundary conditions at the leading order are

$$\frac{\partial p_{in}^{(0)}}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=1} = 0, \quad p_{out}^{(0)} \Big|_{r \rightarrow \infty} = -12 u_{\text{ext}} r \cos \theta, \quad (\text{S47})$$

$$p_{in}^{(0)} \Big|_{r=r_a} = p_{out}^{(0)} \Big|_{r=r_a}, \quad \frac{1}{12} \frac{\partial p_{in}^{(0)}}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=r_a} - u_{r,\text{slip}}^{(0)} \Big|_{r=r_a} = \frac{1}{12} \frac{\partial p_{out}^{(0)}}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=r_a}, \quad (\text{S48})$$

and the leading-order solution is

$$p^{(0)} = \begin{cases} \frac{6}{r_a^2} [(r_a^2 - 1) u_{\text{EOF}} - 2r_a^2 u_{\text{ext}}] \left(r + \frac{1}{r} \right) \cos \theta & 1 < r < r_a \\ \left[\frac{6}{r_a^2} [(r_a^4 - 1) u_{\text{EOF}} - 2r_a^2 u_{\text{ext}}] \frac{1}{r} - 12 u_{\text{ext}} r \right] \cos \theta & r > r_a \end{cases}. \quad (\text{S49})$$

The corresponding leading-order flow field can be expressed in terms of the stream function,

$$\psi^{(0)} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2r_a^2} [(r_a^2 + 1) u_{\text{EOF}} + 2r_a^2 u_{\text{ext}}] \left(r - \frac{1}{r} \right) \sin \theta & 1 < r < r_a \\ \left[\frac{1}{2r_a^2} [(r_a^4 - 1) u_{\text{EOF}} - 2r_a^2 u_{\text{ext}}] \frac{1}{r} + u_{\text{ext}} r \right] \sin \theta & r > r_a \end{cases}. \quad (\text{S50})$$

At the first order, the boundary conditions (S23) and (S24) for the pressure take the form

$$\frac{\partial p_{in}^{(1)}}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=1} = \frac{df(\theta)}{d\theta} \frac{\partial p_{in}^{(0)}}{\partial \theta} \Big|_{r=1} - f(\theta) \frac{\partial^2 p_{in}^{(0)}}{\partial r^2} \Big|_{r=1}, \quad p_{out}^{(1)} \Big|_{r \rightarrow \infty} = 0. \quad (\text{S51})$$

Similarly, the boundary condition (S25) for the continuity of the pressure at $r = r_{\text{cl,sh}}$ at the first order becomes

$$p_{in}^{(1)} \Big|_{r=r_a} + g(\theta) \frac{\partial p_{in}^{(0)}}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=r_a} = p_{out}^{(1)} \Big|_{r=r_a} + g(\theta) \frac{\partial p_{out}^{(0)}}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=r_a}. \quad (\text{S52})$$

Using (S21) and (S20), the boundary condition (S25) for the continuity of the normal velocity can be written as

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}}_{\text{cl,sh}} \cdot \left[-\frac{1}{12} \nabla_{\parallel} p_{in} + \mathbf{u}_{\text{slip}} \right] = \hat{\mathbf{n}}_{\text{cl,sh}} \cdot \left[-\frac{1}{12} \nabla_{\parallel} p_{out} \right] \quad \text{at } r = r_{\text{cl,sh}}. \quad (\text{S53})$$

Making use of the expansions defined in (S41) and (S43), the boundary condition (S53) at the first order takes the form

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{12} \frac{\partial p_{in}^{(1)}}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=r_a} - u_{r,\text{slip}}^{(1)} \Big|_{r=r_a} - \left[\frac{1}{12} \frac{1}{r_a} \frac{\partial p_{in}^{(0)}}{\partial \theta} \Big|_{r=r_a} - u_{\theta,\text{slip}}^{(0)} \Big|_{r=r_a} \right] \frac{1}{r_a} \frac{dg(\theta)}{d\theta} \\ & + \left[\frac{1}{12} \frac{\partial^2 p_{in}^{(0)}}{\partial r^2} \Big|_{r=r_a} - \frac{\partial u_{r,\text{slip}}^{(0)}}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=r_a} \right] g(\theta) = \frac{1}{12} \frac{\partial p_{out}^{(1)}}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=r_a} + \frac{1}{12} g(\theta) \frac{\partial^2 p_{out}^{(0)}}{\partial r^2} \Big|_{r=r_a} - \frac{1}{12} \frac{1}{r_a^2} \frac{dg(\theta)}{d\theta} \frac{\partial p_{out}^{(0)}}{\partial \theta} \Big|_{r=r_a}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S54})$$

We now turn to the first-order solution in the cloaking/shielding region. For convenience, we decompose the inner solution into $p_{in}^{(1)} = p_{in}^{(1),1} + p_{in}^{(1),2}$ and require that $p_{in}^{(1),1}$ and $p_{in}^{(1),2}$ satisfy the boundary conditions (S51) and (S52) in the following form

$$\frac{\partial p_{in}^{(1),1}}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=1} = \frac{df(\theta)}{d\theta} \frac{\partial p_{in}^{(0)}}{\partial \theta} \Big|_{r=1} - f(\theta) \frac{\partial^2 p_{in}^{(0)}}{\partial r^2} \Big|_{r=1}, \quad p_{in}^{(1),1} \Big|_{r=r_a} = 0, \quad (\text{S55})$$

$$\left. \frac{\partial p_{in}^{(1),2}}{\partial r} \right|_{r=1} = 0, \quad p_{in}^{(1),2}|_{r=r_a} = p_{out}^{(1)}|_{r=r_a} + g(\theta) \left[\left. \frac{\partial p_{out}^{(0)}}{\partial r} \right|_{r=r_a} - \left. \frac{\partial p_{in}^{(0)}}{\partial r} \right|_{r=r_a} \right]. \quad (\text{S56})$$

The general solution for $p_{in}^{(1),1}(r, \theta)$ that vanishes at $r = r_a$ is given by

$$p_{in}^{(1),1}(r, \theta) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(r^{-n} - \frac{r^n}{r_a^{2n}} \right) [K_n^1 \cos(n\theta) + K_n^2 \sin(n\theta)]. \quad (\text{S57})$$

To determine the coefficients K_n^1 and K_n^2 , we substitute (S57) into the boundary condition (S55) and obtain

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n(1 + r_a^{-2n}) [K_n^1 \cos(n\theta) + K_n^2 \sin(n\theta)] = \frac{12}{r_a^2} [r_a^2(u_{\text{EOF}} - 2u_{\text{ext}}) - u_{\text{EOF}}] \left[\frac{df(\theta)}{d\theta} \sin\theta + f(\theta) \cos\theta \right]. \quad (\text{S58})$$

Substituting the Fourier series expansion (S33) into (S58) and using the orthogonality properties of the trigonometric functions, yields

$$K_n^1 = \frac{6r_a^{2n-2}}{1 + r_a^{2n}} [r_a^2(u_{\text{EOF}} - 2u_{\text{ext}}) - u_{\text{EOF}}] [a_{n-1} - a_{n+1}], \quad K_n^2 = \frac{6r_a^{2n-2}}{1 + r_a^{2n}} [r_a^2(u_{\text{EOF}} - 2u_{\text{ext}}) - u_{\text{EOF}}] [b_{n-1} - b_{n+1}]. \quad (\text{S59})$$

The general solution for $p_{in}^{(1),2}(r, \theta)$ that satisfies $\partial p_{in}^{(1),2}/\partial r = 0$ at $r = 1$ is given by

$$p_{in}^{(1),2}(r, \theta) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (r^{-n} + r^n) [H_n^1 \cos(n\theta) + H_n^2 \sin(n\theta)]. \quad (\text{S60})$$

The inner pressure $p_{in}^{(1),2}$ and outer pressure $p_{out}^{(1)}$ are coupled through the boundary condition (S56). Thus, to determine the coefficients H_n^1 and H_n^2 we now turn to solve for the outer pressure. Similarly to previous section, a general decaying solution for the pressure is

$$p_{out}^{(1)}(r, \theta) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} r^{-n} [M_n^1 \cos(n\theta) + M_n^2 \sin(n\theta)]. \quad (\text{S61})$$

Before proceeding, we write $g(\theta)$ as a Fourier series expansion

$$g(\theta) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} [d_n \cos(n\theta) + h_n \sin(n\theta)], \quad (\text{S62})$$

where the coefficients d_n and h_n are defined as

$$d_0 = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} g(t) dt, \quad d_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} g(t) \cos(nt) dt, \quad h_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} g(t) \sin(nt) dt, \quad n = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (\text{S63})$$

We note that the Fourier series expansions for $f(\theta)$ and $g(\theta)$, given in (S33) and (S62), will converge for any function differentiable everywhere in the domain. However, discontinuities in the shape function will create "ringing", known as Gibbs phenomenon, and in this case, oscillating deviations will occur near discontinuity points, and will not vanish as the number of terms in the series increases, but will reach a finite value instead. Thus, we expect errors in cloaking/shielding for shapes with discontinuities, and that the magnitude of these errors will increase with the number and magnitude of the discontinuities.

Substituting (S60)–(S62) into the continuity condition (S56) and using the orthogonality properties, we express the coefficients H_n^1 and H_n^2 in terms of M_n^1 and M_n^2 ,

$$H_0^1 = -\frac{6(r_a^2 - 1)u_{\text{EOF}}}{r_a^2} d_1, \quad H_n^1 = \frac{M_n^1 r_a^{-n}}{r_a^n + r_a^{-n}} - \frac{6(r_a^2 - 1)u_{\text{EOF}}}{r_a^2} \frac{d_{n+1} - d_{n-1}}{r_a^n + r_a^{-n}}, \quad n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, \quad (\text{S64})$$

$$H_n^2 = \frac{M_n^2 r_a^{-n}}{r_a^n + r_a^{-n}} - \frac{6(r_a^2 - 1)u_{\text{EOF}}}{r_a^2} \frac{h_{n+1} - h_{n-1}}{r_a^n + r_a^{-n}}, \quad n = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (\text{S65})$$

We are left now with the determination of the coefficients M_n^1 and M_n^2 , using the boundary condition (S54). Substituting the derived expressions for $p_{in}^{(0)}$, $p_{out}^{(0)}$, $\varphi^{(0)}$, $p_{in}^{(1)}$, $p_{out}^{(1)}$, and $\varphi^{(1)}$ into (S54), after some rearrangement we obtain

$$M_n^1 = \frac{6u_{\text{EOF}}}{r_a^{2n}} \left[\left[1 + r_a^{2n-2} \left(1 + 2r_a^2 \frac{u_{\text{ext}}}{u_{\text{EOF}}} \right) \right] (a_{n+1} - a_{n-1}) + r_a^{n-2} \left[(1 + r_a^{2(1+n)})d_{n-1} - (r_a^2 + r_a^{2n})d_{n+1} \right] \right], \quad (\text{S66})$$

$$M_n^2 = \frac{6u_{\text{EOF}}}{r_a^{2n}} \left[\left[1 + r_a^{2n-2} \left(1 + 2r_a^2 \frac{u_{\text{ext}}}{u_{\text{EOF}}} \right) \right] (b_{n+1} - b_{n-1}) + r_a^{n-2} \left[(1 + r_a^{2(1+n)})h_{n-1} - (r_a^2 + r_a^{2n})h_{n+1} \right] \right]. \quad (\text{S67})$$

Combining (S61) and (S66)–(S67) yields a closed-form expression for the first-order outer pressure $p_{out}^{(1)}$. Using this result along with (S57)–(S60) and (S64)–(S65), we obtain a closed-form expression for the first-order solution for the inner pressure $p_{in}^{(1)}$

$$p_{in}^{(1)}(r, \theta) = -\frac{6(r_a^2 - 1)u_{\text{EOF}}}{r_a^2} d_1 + 6u_{\text{EOF}} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{r_a^{2(1+n)} r^n} \left[\Gamma_n^1(r) \cos(n\theta) + \Gamma_n^2(r) \sin(n\theta) \right], \quad (\text{S68})$$

where $\Gamma_n^1(r)$ and $\Gamma_n^2(r)$ are given by

$$\Gamma_n^1(r) = \left[(1 + r^{2n})r_a^2 - r_a^{2n} \left[(r_a^2 - 1) - 2r_a^2 \frac{u_{\text{ext}}}{u_{\text{EOF}}} \right] \right] (a_{n+1} - a_{n-1}) + (1 + r^{2n})r_a^n (d_{n-1} - r_a^2 d_{n+1}), \quad (\text{S69})$$

$$\Gamma_n^2(r) = \left[(1 + r^{2n})r_a^2 - r_a^{2n} \left[(r_a^2 - 1) - 2r_a^2 \frac{u_{\text{ext}}}{u_{\text{EOF}}} \right] \right] (b_{n+1} - b_{n-1}) + (1 + r^{2n})r_a^n (h_{n-1} - r_a^2 h_{n+1}). \quad (\text{S70})$$

S.2.3. Calculation of the hydrodynamic force

In this section, we calculate the leading-order and first-order correction in β to the hydrodynamic force acting on the object in a Hele-Shaw cell. The depth-averaged hydrodynamic force acting on the object is given by

$$\mathbf{F} = \int_{\text{obj}} \boldsymbol{\sigma}|_{r=r_{\text{obj}}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_{\text{obj}} dS, \quad (\text{S71})$$

where dS is the surface element of the deformed object,

$$dS = \sqrt{r_{\text{obj}}^2 + \left(\frac{dr_{\text{obj}}}{d\theta} \right)^2} d\theta = r_{\text{obj}} d\theta + O(\beta^2), \quad (\text{S72})$$

$\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the normalized stress tensor scaled by $\tilde{\mu}\tilde{u}^*/\tilde{r}_0\epsilon^2$,

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \begin{pmatrix} -p + \epsilon^2 \tau_{rr} & \epsilon^2 \tau_{r\theta} \\ \epsilon^2 \tau_{r\theta} & -p + \epsilon^2 \tau_{\theta\theta} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (\text{S73})$$

and $\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_{\text{obj}}$ at $r = r_{\text{obj}}$ is given by

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}|_{r=r_{\text{obj}}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_{\text{obj}} = \left[(-p + \epsilon^2 \tau_{rr}) - \beta \epsilon^2 \tau_{r\theta} \frac{df(\theta)}{d\theta} \right] \hat{\mathbf{r}} + \left[\epsilon^2 \tau_{r\theta} - \beta (-p + \epsilon^2 \tau_{\theta\theta}) \frac{df(\theta)}{d\theta} \right] \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \quad \text{at } r = r_{\text{obj}}. \quad (\text{S74})$$

Here τ_{ij} ($i, j = r, \theta$) are components of the viscous stress contribution to the stress tensor. From (S73) and (S74), it follows that due to the shallow geometry of the Hele-Shaw configuration, the viscous stress contribution is negligible as compared to the pressure contribution. In section S.3, we present the resulting hydrodynamic forces calculated from three-dimensional finite-element simulations, showing that for the considered geometry indeed the contribution of viscous stress is at least one order of magnitude smaller as compared to the pressure contribution. Therefore, in our theoretical analysis, we neglect all the viscous stress terms in (S74), but retain the $O(\beta)$ terms as we are interested

in calculating the first-order correction in β . Based on this assumption, the expression for the hydrodynamic force simplifies to

$$\mathbf{F} = - \int_0^{2\pi} p|_{r=r_{\text{obj}}} \hat{\mathbf{n}}_{\text{obj}} r_{\text{obj}} d\theta, \quad (\text{S75})$$

where $p|_{r=r_{\text{obj}}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_{\text{obj}} r_{\text{obj}}$ are given by

$$p|_{r=r_{\text{obj}}} = p_{in}^{(0)}|_{r=1} + \beta p_{in}^{(1)}|_{r=1} + \beta f(\theta) \frac{\partial p_{in}^{(0)}}{\partial r}|_{r=1} + O(\beta^2), \quad (\text{S76})$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}}_{\text{obj}} r_{\text{obj}} = \left[\hat{\mathbf{r}} - \beta \frac{df(\theta)}{d\theta} \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \right] [1 + \beta f(\theta)] = \hat{\mathbf{r}} - \beta \frac{df(\theta)}{d\theta} \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} + \beta f(\theta) \hat{\mathbf{r}} + O(\beta^2). \quad (\text{S77})$$

At the leading order, the hydrodynamic force corresponds to the force acting on a circular cylinder and is given by

$$\mathbf{F}^{(0)} = - \int_0^{2\pi} p_{in}^{(0)}|_{r=1} \hat{\mathbf{r}} d\theta = - \int_0^{2\pi} p_{in}^{(0)}|_{r=1} [\cos\theta \hat{\mathbf{x}} + \sin\theta \hat{\mathbf{y}}] d\theta. \quad (\text{S78})$$

Using (S49), the leading-order pressure at the surface of the object is $p_{in}^{(0)}|_{r=1} = 12 [u_{\text{EOF}} - 2u_{\text{ext}} - u_{\text{EOF}} r_a^{-2}] \cos\theta$, and thus the leading-order hydrodynamic force reads

$$\mathbf{F}^{(0)} = \frac{12\pi}{r_a^2} [r_a^2 (2u_{\text{ext}} - u_{\text{EOF}}) + u_{\text{EOF}}] \hat{\mathbf{x}}. \quad (\text{S79})$$

Combining (S75), (S76) and (S77) while using (S47) and considering the first order yields

$$\mathbf{F}^{(1)} = - \int_0^{2\pi} \left[[p_{in}^{(1)}|_{r=1} + f(\theta) p_{in}^{(0)}|_{r=1}] \hat{\mathbf{r}} - \frac{df(\theta)}{d\theta} p_{in}^{(0)}|_{r=1} \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} \right] d\theta. \quad (\text{S80})$$

Substituting (S33), (S49) and (S68) into (S80), we obtain the expression for the first-order contribution to the hydrodynamic force $\mathbf{F}^{(1)} = F_x^{(1)} \hat{\mathbf{x}} + F_y^{(1)} \hat{\mathbf{y}}$, where $F_x^{(1)}$ and $F_y^{(1)}$ are

$$F_x^{(1)} = 12\pi(3a_0 - 2a_2)u_{\text{ext}} - \frac{6\pi [2d_0 + r_a(-5a_0 + 4a_2 - 2r_a d_2 + (3a_0 - 2a_2)r_a^2)] u_{\text{EOF}}}{r_a^3}, \quad (\text{S81})$$

$$F_y^{(1)} = -24\pi b_2 u_{\text{ext}} + \frac{12\pi [h_2 r_a + b_2 (r_a^2 - 2)] u_{\text{EOF}}}{r_a^2}. \quad (\text{S82})$$

It is worth noting that only the terms corresponding to $n = 0$ and $n = 2$ in the expressions for the shapes of the object and cloaking/shielding region, (S33) and (S62), contribute to the first-order force, similar to the force exerted on a slightly deformed sphere in the Stokes flow [9, 10]. For comparison, it is also worth noting that in the absence of electro-osmotic flow the hydrodynamic force acting on the slightly deformed object is

$$\mathbf{F}^{(0)} = 24\pi u_{\text{ext}} \hat{\mathbf{x}}, \quad (\text{S83})$$

$$\mathbf{F}^{(1)} = 12\pi u_{\text{ext}} [(3a_0 - 2a_2) \hat{\mathbf{x}} - 2b_2 \hat{\mathbf{y}}]. \quad (\text{S84})$$

S.2.4. Cloaking conditions

In this section, we determine the conditions for hydrodynamic cloaking, obtaining the relation between u_{ext} and u_{EOF} and the shape of the cloaking region $g(\theta)$, such that the flow outside this region is "unaware" of the presence of the object. To cloak the object hydrodynamically, we require the flow field in the outer region to attain a uniform value u_{ext} the along x -axis,

$$\langle \mathbf{u}_{\parallel} \rangle_{\text{out}} \equiv u_{\text{ext}} \hat{\mathbf{x}}, \quad (\text{S85})$$

and from the asymptotic expansion (S42) obtain

$$\langle \mathbf{u}_{\parallel} \rangle_{out}^{(0)} \equiv u_{\text{ext}} \hat{\mathbf{x}} \quad \text{and} \quad \langle \mathbf{u}_{\parallel} \rangle_{out}^{(1)} \equiv 0. \quad (\text{S86})$$

Outside the cloaking region the pressure is related to the velocity field through $\langle \mathbf{u}_{\parallel} \rangle = -\nabla_{\parallel} p/12$, subjected to the boundary condition $p = -12u_{\text{ext}}r \cos \theta$ as $r \rightarrow \infty$, and therefore the condition (S86) can be expressed in terms of the pressure as

$$p_{out}^{(0)} = -12u_{\text{ext}}r \cos \theta = -12u_{\text{ext}}x \quad \text{and} \quad p_{out}^{(1)} \equiv 0. \quad (\text{S87})$$

From (S49) and (S50), it follows that the outer flow and pressure satisfy the leading-order requirements (S86) and (S87) provided

$$u_{\text{EOF}} = \frac{2r_a^2}{r_a^4 - 1} u_{\text{ext}}. \quad (\text{S88})$$

To satisfy the first-order condition $p_{out}^{(1)} \equiv 0$ in (S87), we require the coefficients M_n^1 and M_n^2 appearing in (S61) to vanish. Substituting (S88) into (S66) and (S67), we obtain that at the first order the cloaking condition is satisfied provided

$$\left[1 + r_a^{2(n+1)} \right] (a_{n+1} - a_{n-1}) + r_a^{n-2} (1 + r_a^{2(1+n)}) d_{n-1} - r_a^n (1 + r_a^{2(n-1)}) d_{n+1} = 0, \quad (\text{S89})$$

and

$$\left[1 + r_a^{2(n+1)} \right] (b_{n+1} - b_{n-1}) + r_a^{n-2} (1 + r_a^{2(1+n)}) h_{n-1} - r_a^n (1 + r_a^{2(n-1)}) h_{n+1} = 0. \quad (\text{S90})$$

The recursive equations (S89) and (S90) define the shape of the cloaking region relating it to the shape of the object. Rearranging and changing the subscripts according to $n \rightarrow n + 1$ yields

$$d_n = r_a^2 \frac{1 + r_a^{2n}}{1 + r_a^{2(n+2)}} d_{n+2} - \frac{1}{r_a^{n-1}} (a_{n+2} - a_n), \quad h_n = r_a^2 \frac{1 + r_a^{2n}}{1 + r_a^{2(n+2)}} h_{n+2} - \frac{1}{r_a^{n-1}} (b_{n+2} - b_n), \quad (\text{S91})$$

or

$$d_{n+2} = \frac{1 + r_a^{2(n+2)}}{r_a^2 (1 + r_a^{2n})} \left[d_n + \frac{1}{r_a^{n-1}} (a_{n+2} - a_n) \right], \quad h_{n+2} = \frac{1 + r_a^{2(n+2)}}{r_a^2 (1 + r_a^{2n})} \left[h_n + \frac{1}{r_a^{n-1}} (b_{n+2} - b_n) \right]. \quad (\text{S92})$$

Clearly, because of the recursive nature of (S91) and (S92) there is freedom in the choice of four coefficients d_{n+1} , d_{n+2} , h_{n+1} and h_{n+2} , which affects the values and the number of non-vanishing coefficients. To obtain a finite number of non-vanishing coefficients d_n and h_n , we first define n_{max} as the maximum subscript of the non-vanishing coefficients a_n and b_n . Thus, $a_n = b_n \equiv 0$ for $n > n_{\text{max}}$. Next, we set

$$d_{n_{\text{max}}+1} = d_{n_{\text{max}}+2} = h_{n_{\text{max}}+1} = h_{n_{\text{max}}+2} = 0. \quad (\text{S93})$$

From (S79)–(S93) and the definition of n_{max} , it follows that the coefficients with larger values of the subscript also vanish,

$$d_n = 0, \quad h_n = 0 \quad \text{for} \quad n > n_{\text{max}} + 2, \quad (\text{S94})$$

and the cloaking region is defined by $d_n = \{d_0, d_1, d_2, \dots, d_{n_{\text{max}}}\}$ and $h_n = \{h_1, h_2, \dots, h_{n_{\text{max}}}\}$, where d_n and h_n are determined from (S91) and (S93). In summary, under the cloaking conditions (S88), (S91) and (S93) the outer flow is "unaware" of the presence of the object.

It is interesting to calculate the hydrodynamic force under cloaking conditions and compare it with the case of pressure-driven flow. Substituting (S88) into (S79) and (S81)–(S82), we find

$$\mathbf{F}^{(0)} = 24\pi u_{\text{ext}} \frac{r_a^2}{r_a^2 + 1} \hat{\mathbf{x}}, \quad (\text{S95})$$

$$\mathbf{F}^{(1)} = \frac{12u_{\text{ext}}\pi}{r_a^4 - 1} \left[\frac{-2d_0 + r_a(2d_2r_a + 2a_2(r_a^2 - r_a^4 - 1)) + a_0(2 - 3r_a^2 + 3r_a^4)}{r_a} \hat{\mathbf{x}} + 2[h_2r_a + b_2(r_a^2 - r_a^4 - 1)] \hat{\mathbf{y}} \right]. \quad (\text{S96})$$

As we can see, the leading-order hydrodynamic force is smaller by a factor $r_a^2/(r_a^2 + 1)$ than the hydrodynamic force $\mathbf{F}^{(0)} = 24\pi u_{\text{ext}} \hat{\mathbf{x}}$ in the case of pressure-driven flow. Thus, under cloaking conditions, there is no significant shielding of the object from the hydrodynamic force.

S.2.5. Shielding conditions

In this section, we determine the conditions for hydrodynamic shielding, obtaining a relation between u_{ext} and u_{EOF} , and the shape of the shielding region $g(\theta)$ required to eliminate the hydrodynamic force. From (S79), it follows that the leading-order hydrodynamic force vanishes provided

$$u_{\text{EOF}} = \frac{2r_a^2}{r_a^2 - 1} u_{\text{ext}}. \quad (\text{S97})$$

Importantly, substituting the condition (S97) into (S49), we find that under shielding conditions the pressure is identically zero in the inner region at the leading order, i.e. $p_{in}^{(0)} \equiv 0$ within $1 \leq r \leq r_a$. Using the condition (S97), the expression for hydrodynamic force at the first order, (S81) and (S82), reduces to

$$\mathbf{F}^{(1)} = -\frac{24u_{\text{ext}}\pi}{r_a(r_a^2 - 1)} [[d_0 - r_a a_0 - r_a(r_a d_2 - a_2)]\hat{\mathbf{x}} + r_a(b_2 - r_a h_2)\hat{\mathbf{y}}]. \quad (\text{S98})$$

The first-order hydrodynamic force (S98) vanishes provided that the coefficients d_0 , d_2 , and h_2 of the shielding region are chosen as

$$d_0 = r_a a_0, \quad d_2 = \frac{a_2}{r_a}, \quad h_2 = \frac{b_2}{r_a}. \quad (\text{S99})$$

We note that (S99) partially defines the shape of the shielding region, relating it to the shape of the object. The remaining coefficients are determined from examination of the electro-osmotic slip boundary condition at the surface of the object, as shown in the next section.

S.2.5.1. Electro-osmotic slip velocity at the surface of the object

Thus far, we found a restriction only on three coefficients d_0 , d_2 , and h_2 of the shielding region $g(\theta)$. In this section, we determine the remaining coefficients by considering the fulfillment of the electro-osmotic slip boundary condition at the surface of the object.

Within the Hele-Shaw approximation considering only the leading order in ϵ , the boundary condition for the tangential velocity at the surface of the object cannot be satisfied in general. As an example, consider case of a circular object with $\beta = 0$, corresponding to the leading-order solution. From (S50), it follows that the tangential velocity at the surface is

$$\langle u_\theta \rangle_{in}^{(0)} = -\frac{1}{r_a^2} [r_a^2(u_{\text{EOF}} + 2u_{\text{ext}}) + u_{\text{EOF}}] \sin\theta \quad \text{at } r = 1, \quad (\text{S100})$$

violating the electro-osmotic slip boundary condition, $-2u_{\text{EOF}}\sin\theta$ at the surface. Resolving this violation would require a higher-order correction of the flow field in the vicinity of the object to achieve a physically correct solution. This correction is characterized by high gradients of the velocity in the direction normal to the object, leading to significant shear stress on the surface and consequently to contributions of the viscous force [11]. However, when satisfying the electro-osmotic slip condition at the surface, such a correction is not required, and the viscous contribution to the hydrodynamic force is significantly reduced. Importantly, when choosing u_{EOF} according to (S97), such that the leading-order contribution to the force vanishes, resulting in the fulfillment of the electro-osmotic slip boundary condition on the surface at the leading order.

More generically speaking, the electro-osmotic slip boundary condition is

$$\langle \mathbf{u}_\parallel \rangle |_{r=r_{\text{obj}}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{\text{obj}} = -\langle \zeta \rangle \nabla_\parallel \varphi |_{r=r_{\text{obj}}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{\text{obj}}, \quad (\text{S101})$$

and from (S12), $\langle \mathbf{u}_\parallel \rangle = -\nabla_\parallel p/12 - \langle \zeta \rangle \nabla_\parallel \varphi$, it follows that the slip condition is satisfied provided

$$\nabla_\parallel p_{in} |_{r=r_{\text{obj}}} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{\text{obj}} = 0, \quad (\text{S102})$$

Since under the condition (S97) $p_{in}^{(0)} \equiv 0$ within the shielding region, the requirement (S102) is automatically satisfied at the leading order. At first order, the requirement (S102) becomes

$$\frac{\partial p_{in}^{(1)}}{\partial \theta} |_{r=1} = 0. \quad (\text{S103})$$

Cylinder	Theory Finite-element simulations	
Pressure-driven flow		
Pressure contribution to force	1	1.04
Viscous stress contribution to force	0	0.04
Hydrodynamic shielding		
Pressure contribution to force	0	-0.09
Viscous stress contribution to force	0	-3.5×10^{-3}
Hydrodynamic cloaking		
Pressure contribution to force	0.8	0.81
Viscous stress contribution to force	0	0.03

TABLE S1. Comparison of theoretical predictions and finite-element simulation results for the pressure and viscous stress contributions to the force acting on the cylinder in a Hele-Shaw cell. All force contributions were normalized by $\tilde{F}^* = 24\pi\tilde{\mu}\tilde{u}_{\text{ext}}\tilde{r}_0^2/\tilde{h}$. In the case of pressure-driven flow and shielding \tilde{F}^* is 5.13×10^{-10} N, and in the case of cloaking \tilde{F}^* is 2.57×10^{-9} N.

Using (S68) and (S97), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial p_{in}^{(1)}}{\partial \theta} \Big|_{r=1} = & \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{12u_{\text{EOF}}n}{r_a^{2n}} \left[[(b_{n+1} - b_{n-1}) + r_a^{n-2}(h_{n-1} - r_a^2 h_{n+1})] \cos(n\theta) \right. \\ & \left. - [(a_{n+1} - a_{n-1}) + r_a^{n-2}(d_{n-1} - r_a^2 d_{n+1})] \sin(n\theta) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S104})$$

When setting

$$d_n = \frac{a_n}{r_a^{n-1}}, \quad h_n = \frac{b_n}{r_a^{n-1}}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, \quad (\text{S105})$$

the electro-osmotic slip condition is satisfied. We note that (S105) completely defines the shape of the shielding region relative to the shape of the object and is consistent with the condition (S99).

In summary, under the shielding conditions (S97) and (S105) and under the approximations made, the hydrodynamic force acting on the object vanishes and the electro-osmotic slip condition is satisfied. Furthermore, the leading-order pressure in the shielding region is identically zero, whereas the first-order pressure is uniform and is given by

$$p_{in}^{(1)} \equiv -\frac{6(r_a^2 - 1)u_{\text{EOF}}}{r_a^2} a_1. \quad (\text{S106})$$

We note that the Fourier coefficient a_1 corresponds to the position of the center of mass of the object relative to the x -axis.

S.3. FINITE-ELEMENT NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

S.3.1. Comparison of theoretical predictions and numerical results

To validate the theoretical results, we performed finite-element numerical simulations using the commercial software COMSOL Multiphysics (version 5.4, COMSOL AB, Stockholm, Sweden). Details regarding the governing equations, boundary conditions, domain discretization, and physical parameters employed in the finite-element numerical simulations are provided in the subsequent section.

We first performed finite-element simulations of the flow around a circular cylinder in a Hele-Shaw cell. Figure S2 presents a comparison of theoretical predictions and finite-element simulation results corresponding to pressure-driven flow (a,d,g), shielding (b,e,h), and cloaking (c,f,i) conditions. Figure S2(a-f) presents the resulting pressure distribution (colormap) and streamlines (white lines), showing an excellent agreement between the theoretical predictions and the finite-element simulations for all three cases. In Fig. S2(g-i) we compare analytically (dashed lines) and numerically (solid lines) obtained streamlines, also showing an excellent agreement.

FIG. S2. Comparison of theoretical predictions and finite-element simulation results for the case of a cylindrical object. (a)–(f) Analytical (a,b,c) and numerical (d,e,f) results for the pressure distribution (colormap) and streamlines (white lines), corresponding to pressure-driven flow (a,d), shielding (b,e), and cloaking (c,f) conditions. (g,h,i) Comparison between analytical (dashed lines) and numerical (solid lines) streamlines corresponding to pressure-driven flow (g), shielding (h), and cloaking (i) conditions. In the case of pressure-driven flow and shielding, the external velocity is $\tilde{u}_{\text{ext}} = 10.2 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$, and in the case of cloaking the external velocity is $\tilde{u}_{\text{ext}} = 51.0 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$. The shielding and cloaking regions (purple lines) are circles with $\tilde{r}_a = 2\tilde{r}_0$ and $\tilde{u}_{\text{EOF}} = 27.2 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$.

To characterize the effect of hydrodynamic shielding, we calculated the pressure and viscous stress contributions to the hydrodynamic force acting on a cylindrical-shaped object under pressure-driven flow, cloaking and shielding conditions. Table S1 presents the comparison of the resulting forces in non-dimensional form based on the theoretical calculations and the finite-element simulations, clearly indicating that the viscous stress contribution is negligible as compared to pressure contribution in all cases. We normalized all forces by (S83), written in dimensional form as $\tilde{F}^* = 24\pi\tilde{\mu}\tilde{u}_{\text{ext}}\tilde{r}_0^2/\tilde{h}$ and corresponding to the theoretically predicted hydrodynamic force acting on a cylinder in the case of pressure-driven flow. For the cases of pressure-driven flow and cloaking conditions, we observe a very good agreement between the theoretical and simulation results for the pressure contribution. Yet, as expected, the Hele-Shaw theory fails to predict the viscous stress contribution. Within the framework of the Hele-Shaw theory, the calculation of the viscous stress contribution requires the consideration of a $O(\epsilon)$ boundary layer next to the cylindrical surface (see [11]), and is beyond the scope of this work. Under shielding conditions, the finite-element simulation results show one order-of-magnitude reduction in the hydrodynamics force. Interestingly, we obtain a “negative” drag acting on the cylinder in $-\hat{x}$ direction, indicating that our theoretical model slightly overpredicts the value of u_{EOF} required to achieve a perfect shielding.

Extending our analysis to more complex shapes, we also considered the case of a flower-shaped object parameterized by

$$r_{\text{obj}} = 1 + \beta f(\theta) = 1 - \beta \cos(5\theta). \quad (\text{S107})$$

Flower	Theory	Finite-element simulations
Pressure-driven flow		
Pressure contribution to force	1	1.09
Viscous stress contribution to force	0	0.04
Hydrodynamic shielding		
Pressure contribution to force	0	-0.08
Viscous stress contribution to force	0	-2.7×10^{-3}
Hydrodynamic cloaking		
Pressure contribution to force	0.8	0.84
Viscous stress contribution to force	0	0.03

TABLE S2. Comparison of theoretical predictions and finite-element simulation results for the pressure and viscous stress contributions to the force acting on the flower-shaped object in a Hele-Shaw cell. All force contributions were normalized by $\tilde{F}^* = 24\pi\tilde{\mu}\tilde{u}_{\text{ext}}\tilde{r}_0^2/\tilde{h}$. In the case of pressure-driven flow and shielding \tilde{F}^* is 4.96×10^{-10} N, and in the case of cloaking \tilde{F}^* is 2.48×10^{-9} N.

Using (S91) and (S105), the corresponding shapes of the cloaking and shielding regions are

$$r_{\text{cl}} = r_a + \beta [0.21 \cos(\theta) + 0.35 \cos(3\theta) - 0.20 \cos(5\theta)], \quad r_{\text{sh}} = r_a - 0.20\beta \cos(5\theta). \quad (\text{S108})$$

Figure S3 presents a comparison of theoretical predictions and finite-element simulation results for the flower-shaped object, corresponding to pressure-driven flow (a,d,g), shielding (b,e,h), and cloaking (c,f,i) conditions, with $r_a = 2$ and $\beta = 0.1$. Figure S3(a-f) presents the resulting pressure distribution (colormap) and streamlines (white lines), showing a good agreement between the theoretical predictions and the finite-element simulations for all three cases. In Fig. S3(g-i) we compare analytically (dashed lines) and numerically (solid lines) obtained streamlines, also showing an excellent agreement.

Table S2 presents the comparison of the resulting forces in non-dimensional form acting on a flower-shaped object under pressure-driven flow, cloaking and shielding conditions, based on the theoretical calculations and the finite-element simulations. We normalized all forces by (S83) and (S84) in dimensional form, which corresponds to the theoretically predicted hydrodynamic force acting on a slightly-deformed cylinder in the case of pressure-driven flow. Similarly to the case of a cylinder, we observe a very good agreement between the theoretical and the simulation results for the pressure contribution, while the viscous contribution is negligible, indicating that the use of the shielding conditions (S97) and (S105) enables achieving a hydrodynamic force reduction by one order of magnitude.

S.3.2. Details of finite-element numerical simulations

We performed three-dimensional finite-element simulations with the commercial software COMSOL Multiphysics (version 5.4, COMSOL AB, Stockholm, Sweden) by coupling the Creeping Flow module to the Electrostatics module. Specifically, we coupled the Navier-Stokes equations (S1) (without inertia term) to the Laplace equation for the electrostatic potential (S4) through the Helmholtz–Smoluchowski slip boundary condition (S2), which uses the electric field obtained from the solution of the Laplace equation. The boundary conditions used in the finite-element simulations are summarized in Table S3.

We discretized the domain with six uniformly distributed elements in the transverse dimension and used a non-uniform unstructured grid spacing in the $\tilde{x} - \tilde{y}$ plane with high resolution in the cloaking/shielding region. For such coupling, the COMSOL solver employs second-order (quadratic) elements for the flow field and the electrostatic potential, and first-order (linear) elements for the pressure field. All simulations converged such that the residual reduced by at least five orders of magnitude relative to the initial guess. We performed mesh independence tests using meshes of 47000, 85000, and 167000 elements, which showed that the resulting force on the object varied by less than 2%. All the presented results were obtained using the finest mesh.

Tables S4 summarizes the values of physical and geometrical parameters used in the finite-element simulations.

FIG. S3. Comparison of theoretical predictions and finite-element simulation results for the case of a flower-shaped object. (a)–(f) Analytical (a,b,c) and numerical (d,e,f) results for the pressure distribution (colormap) and streamlines (white lines), corresponding to pressure-driven flow (a,d), shielding (b,e), and cloaking (c,f) conditions. (g,h,i) Comparison between analytical (dashed lines) and numerical (solid lines) streamlines corresponding to pressure-driven flow (g), shielding (h), and cloaking (i) conditions. In the case of pressure-driven flow and shielding, the external velocity is $\tilde{u}_{\text{ext}} = 9.86 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$, and in the case of cloaking the external velocity is $\tilde{u}_{\text{ext}} = 49.3 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$. The shielding and cloaking regions (purple lines) are defined by (S117) with $\tilde{r}_a = 2\tilde{r}_0$, $\beta = 0.1$, and $\tilde{u}_{\text{EOF}} = 26.3 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$.

S.4. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

S.4.1. Design of the microfluidic device

FIG. S4. Schematic of the microfluidic device used in the experiments. The object and the gate electrode are located in section c, which is connected at both ends to tapered regions (section b), narrow channels (section a), and reservoirs.

We experimentally demonstrate the hydrodynamic cloaking and shielding using the microfluidic device schematized

Boundary	Velocity/Pressure (PDF)	Velocity/Pressure (PDF+EOF)	Electric potential (PDF+EOF)
Left boundary (inlet): $\tilde{x} = -\tilde{L}/2$	Normal inflow velocity: $\tilde{u} = \tilde{u}_{ext}$	Normal inflow velocity: $\tilde{u} = \tilde{u}_{ext}$	Constant voltage: $\tilde{\varphi} = \tilde{E}\tilde{L}$
Right boundary (outlet): $\tilde{x} = \tilde{L}/2$	Uniform pressure: $\tilde{p} = 0$	Uniform pressure: $\tilde{p} = 0$	Grounded: $\tilde{\varphi} = 0$
Side boundaries: $\tilde{y} = \pm\tilde{W}/2$	Slip: $\partial\tilde{u}/\partial\tilde{y} = \partial\tilde{w}/\partial\tilde{y} = 0$	Slip: $\partial\tilde{u}/\partial\tilde{y} = \partial\tilde{w}/\partial\tilde{y} = 0$	Insulation: $\partial\tilde{\varphi}/\partial\tilde{y} = 0$
	No-penetration: $\tilde{v} = 0$	No-penetration: $\tilde{v} = 0$	
Object surface: $\tilde{r} = \tilde{r}_{obj}$	No-slip: $\hat{\mathbf{t}}_{obj} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{u}} = 0$	Electro-osmotic slip: $\hat{\mathbf{t}}_{obj} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{u}} = \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{obj} \cdot [\tilde{\varepsilon}\tilde{\zeta}_0 \tilde{\nabla} \tilde{\varphi} / \tilde{\mu}]$	Insulation: $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_{obj} \cdot \tilde{\nabla} \tilde{\varphi} = 0$
	No-penetration: $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_{obj} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{u}} = 0$	No-penetration: $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_{obj} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{u}} = 0$	
Top/bottom wall: $\tilde{z} = 0, \tilde{h}$ and $\tilde{r}_{obj} \leq \tilde{r} \leq \tilde{r}_{cl}$	No-slip: $\tilde{u} = \tilde{v} = 0$	Electro-osmotic slip: $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{\parallel} = \tilde{\varepsilon}\tilde{\zeta}_0 \tilde{\nabla} \tilde{\varphi}_{\parallel} / \tilde{\mu}$	Insulation: $\partial\tilde{\varphi}/\partial\tilde{z} = 0$
Cloaking region	No-penetration: $\tilde{w} = 0$	No-penetration: $\tilde{w} = 0$	
Top/bottom wall: $\tilde{z} = 0, \tilde{h}$ and $\tilde{r} \geq \tilde{r}_{cl}$	No-slip: $\tilde{u} = \tilde{v} = 0$	No-slip: $\tilde{u} = \tilde{v} = 0$	Insulation: $\partial\tilde{\varphi}/\partial\tilde{z} = 0$
Outside cloaking region	No-penetration: $\tilde{w} = 0$	No-penetration: $\tilde{w} = 0$	

TABLE S3. Summary of the boundary conditions used in the finite-element simulations. ‘‘PDF’’ refers to pressure-driven flow and ‘‘EOF’’ to electro-osmotic flow.

in Fig. S4. The object and the gate electrode are located in an unobstructed chamber (indicated with the letter c), which is connected to two reservoirs via tapered sections containing pillars (indicated with the letter b) and narrow channels (indicated with the letter a). We generate an electric field inside the chamber by using two driving electrodes located at both edges of the chamber.

We generate a pressure-driven flow along the chamber by imposing a pressure difference between the two reservoirs, denoted as $\Delta\tilde{p}_{tot}$. To obtain a rough estimation of the pressure drop across the chamber (section c), and thus the resulting flow velocity, we describe the hydraulic resistance of each section (a, b, c) as [12]

$$\tilde{R}_j^H = \frac{12\tilde{\mu}\tilde{l}_j}{1 - 0.63(\tilde{h}/\tilde{w}_j)} \frac{1}{\tilde{h}^3\tilde{w}_j}, \quad (\text{S109})$$

where $\tilde{h} = 15 \mu\text{m}$ is the height, \tilde{l}_j is the length, and \tilde{w}_j is the width of the j -th section, respectively. Since the width of the tapered regions varies along the flow path, we assign an effective width to these regions. The area of section b outside the pillars is 7.5 mm^2 , which over length $\tilde{l}_b = 3 \text{ mm}$ corresponds to an effective width of $\tilde{w}_{b,eff} = 2.5 \text{ mm}$. The pressure drop $\Delta\tilde{p}_c$ across the chamber can be expressed as

$$\Delta\tilde{p}_c = \frac{\tilde{R}_c^H}{2(\tilde{R}_a^H + \tilde{R}_b^H) + \tilde{R}_c^H} \Delta\tilde{p}_{tot} \approx \frac{1}{145} \Delta\tilde{p}_{tot}. \quad (\text{S110})$$

Physical property	Notation	Value	Units
Gap between the plates	\tilde{h}	15	μm
Radius of object	\tilde{r}_0	100	μm
Radius of cloaking region	$\tilde{r}_a = 2\tilde{r}_0$	200	μm
Length of computational domain	$\tilde{L} = 20\tilde{r}_0$	2	mm
Width of computational domain	$\tilde{W} = 14\tilde{r}_0$	1.4	mm
Viscosity of fluid	$\tilde{\mu}$	10^{-3}	Pa s
Permittivity of fluid	$\tilde{\epsilon}$	7.08×10^{-10}	F m^{-1}
Electric field far from object	\tilde{E}	3×10^4	V m^{-1}
Cylindrical object ($\beta = 0$)			
Electro-osmotic slip velocity	$\tilde{u}_{\text{EOF}} = -\tilde{\epsilon}\tilde{\zeta}_0\tilde{E}/\tilde{\mu}$	27.2	$\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$
External velocity (shielding)	\tilde{u}_{ext}	10.2	$\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$
External velocity (cloaking)	\tilde{u}_{ext}	51.0	$\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$
Flower-shaped object ($\beta = 0.1$)			
Electro-osmotic slip velocity	$\tilde{u}_{\text{EOF}} = -\tilde{\epsilon}\tilde{\zeta}_0\tilde{E}/\tilde{\mu}$	26.3	$\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$
External velocity (shielding)	\tilde{u}_{ext}	9.86	$\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$
External velocity (cloaking)	\tilde{u}_{ext}	49.3	$\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$

TABLE S4. Values of physical and geometrical parameters used in the finite-element simulations.

FIG. S5. Illustration of the fabrication steps. We pattern the electrode using a lift-off process (1), then we deposit a dielectric layer using PECVD (2) and open the electric connection by wet etching (3). We fabricate the object and the microfluidic channels from SU8 (4) and we seal the device with a flat piece of PDMS with holes for the reservoirs (5).

The resulting average flow velocity inside the chamber can be then expressed as

$$\tilde{u}_c = \frac{\Delta\tilde{p}_c}{\tilde{R}_c^H \tilde{\omega}_c \tilde{h}}. \quad (\text{S111})$$

Using a water column with filling heights ranging between 0 and 30 cm, corresponding to pressure drops across the chamber of 0–20 Pa, we can produce a flow velocity of up to $85 \mu\text{m/s}$.

S.4.2. Fabrication of microfluidic device

We fabricate the devices using the approach detailed in Paratore *et al.* [13] that we report here in brief for completeness. Figure S5 shows schematics of the fabrication steps. We define the gate and driving electrodes by a lift-off process using a 2 nm thick Pt layer sandwiched between two 2 nm thick Ti layers on a borosilicate glass wafer. We then deposit a dielectric composed of 500 nm SiON followed by 100 nm of SiO₂ by plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD) to ensure electric insulation between the liquid and the gate electrode. We open the electric connection by buffered hydrofluoric acid (BHF) etching of the dielectric. To define the microfluidic channels and the object, we spin-coat and pattern a 15- μm -thick layer of SU8 photoresist on top of the wafer. Finally, we

dice the wafer, and bond each device to a flat piece of polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) with punched holes for the two reservoirs.

S.4.3. Experimental setup

We control the pressure-driven flow by using a water column connected to one of the reservoirs of the device to create a pressure differential between the two reservoirs, and the EOF on top of the gate electrode by using alternating current field-effect electro-osmosis (ac-FEEO) [13]. In ac-FEEO, the zeta potential on the gate electrode region is set by applying an AC potential difference between the gate electrode and the bulk liquid, in sync with the driving electric field along the chamber. The resulting time averaged EOF is zero outside the electrode region, whereas it can be dynamically controlled on top of the gate electrode by tuning the gate potential and the driving electric field.

We mount the device on a homemade connector fixed on the stage of an epi-fluorescence inverted microscope (eclipse TI, Nikon, magnification 4x, NA = 0.13, illumination Nikon Intensilight). The connector is composed of a 3D printed part and a printed circuit board (PCB) containing electric pins interfacing the device with power supplies (Keithley 2410, Tektronix). We use one power supply to create the driving electric field inside the microfluidic chamber and another to control the potential on the gate electrode. Both power supplies provide square-wave signals with a frequency of 25 Hz. In all experiments we apply electric potentials (peak to peak) of 50 V to the gate and 100 V to the driving electrodes (corresponding to electric field of 200 V/cm).

At the beginning of each experiment, we first fill the channel with ethanol, then with de-ionized water, and finally with an aqueous buffer (10 mM acetic acid, 1 mM NaOH, pH 3.8) containing fluorescent polystyrene particles (diameter = 0.83 μm , Spherotech Inc). To achieve a uniform distribution of the particles, we match the buffer mass density to that of the polystyrene particles using a 50 vol-% D₂O/H₂O solution. The particles are imaged using a TRITC filter (Nikon, 525/40 excitation, 605/55 emission, and 565 nm dichroic mirror). We record the motion of the particles with a CCD camera (Clara, Andor-Oxford Instruments) with a 30 ms exposure time and a frame rate of 7 fps.

S.4.4. Choice of experimental parameters

We acquire and analyze the flow field by using fluorescent tracer particles and the particle image velocimetry (PIV) method [14]. The flow field is a superposition of pressure-driven flow and EOF, which can be independently controlled experimentally. While in each experiment we measure the mean pressure-driven flow velocity \tilde{u}_{ext} by averaging velocity vectors far from the object where the flow is uniform and independent of EOF, the value of \tilde{u}_{EOF} cannot be directly measured, since on top of the gate electrode, a pressure-driven flow is always present in addition to EOF. Furthermore, the EOF velocity generated by the gate electrode cannot be directly estimated, as there is no straightforward analytical relation between the gate potential and the induced zeta potential at the solid-liquid interface. Therefore, to determine the value of \tilde{u}_{EOF} we developed a fitting strategy described in the next subsection (see S4.1.1).

We use the obtained value of \tilde{u}_{EOF} to calculate the associated pressure-driven flow leading to cloaking and shielding conditions according to the theoretical model, given in (S88) and (S97). We then perform a series of experiments imposing different pressure-driven velocities around these points. Finally, we obtain the experimental flow field for each case, compare it with the theoretically predicted flow field satisfying cloaking or shielding conditions and find the best fit between experiments and theory (see S4.4.2).

S.4.4.1. Fitting of the electro-osmotic flow velocity

We acquire the velocity field solely due to the gate electrode by fixing the gate potential and applying a driving electric field in the absence of any externally imposed pressure-driven flow. Performing a PIV analysis, we obtain an experimental flow field that we denote as $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{ij}^{\text{exp}} = (\tilde{u}_{ij}^{\text{exp}}, \tilde{v}_{ij}^{\text{exp}})$, where the coordinates of each position vector in the physical domain is given by $\tilde{x} = (i - 1)\Delta\tilde{x}$ and $\tilde{y} = (j - 1)\Delta\tilde{y}$, where $i = 1, \dots, M$, $j = 1, \dots, N$, and $\Delta\tilde{x}$ and $\Delta\tilde{y}$ measure the pixel size defined by the PIV analysis. We fit this experimental flow field to the theoretical flow field, which in case of the cylindrical object is given by

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}}^{\text{th}} = \frac{\tilde{u}_{\text{EOF}}}{2} \frac{\tilde{r}_a^2 + \tilde{r}_0^2}{\tilde{r}_a^2} \begin{cases} \left(1 + \frac{\tilde{r}_0^2(\tilde{y}^2 - \tilde{x}^2)}{(\tilde{x}^2 + \tilde{y}^2)^2}\right) \hat{\mathbf{x}} - \frac{2\tilde{r}_0^2\tilde{x}\tilde{y}}{(\tilde{x}^2 + \tilde{y}^2)^2} \hat{\mathbf{y}} & \tilde{r}_0 < \tilde{r} < \tilde{r}_a \\ \frac{(\tilde{x}^2 - \tilde{y}^2)(\tilde{r}_a^2 - \tilde{r}_0^2)}{(\tilde{x}^2 + \tilde{y}^2)^2} \hat{\mathbf{x}} + \frac{2\tilde{x}\tilde{y}(\tilde{r}_a^2 - \tilde{r}_0^2)}{(\tilde{x}^2 + \tilde{y}^2)^2} \hat{\mathbf{y}} & \tilde{r} > \tilde{r}_a \end{cases}, \quad (\text{S112})$$

FIG. S6. Experimental (blue) and analytical (red) velocity field around a (a) cylindrical and (b) flower-shaped object due to non-uniform electro-osmotic flow generated by a gate electrode (indicated by the purple line).

where

$$\tilde{u}_{\text{EOF}} = -\frac{\tilde{\varepsilon} \langle \tilde{\zeta} \rangle \tilde{E}}{\tilde{\mu}}, \quad (\text{S113})$$

and wherein $\langle \tilde{\zeta} \rangle$ is the depth-averaged value of the zeta potential in the cloaking/shielding region, and \tilde{E} is the magnitude of the electric field far from the object. Similar expressions can be derived for a butterfly-shaped object using (S21), (S44), (S45), (S49), (S61) and (S68) providing the leading- and first-order solution. The expression for the leading-order solution is given in (S112) for the case of a cylindrical object, whereas the expression for the first-order correction is lengthy and cumbersome, and thus for brevity we do not provide it here.

We fit the parameter \tilde{u}_{EOF} such that theoretical flow field best fits the experimental one, by minimization of the function F_{fit} defined as

$$F_{\text{fit}}(\tilde{u}_{\text{EOF}}) = \frac{1}{MN} \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} f_{\text{fit},ij}^2(\tilde{u}_{\text{EOF}}), \quad (\text{S114})$$

where

$$f_{\text{fit},ij} = \sqrt{\frac{(\tilde{u}_{ij}^{\text{th}} - \tilde{u}_{ij}^{\text{exp}})^2 + (\tilde{v}_{ij}^{\text{th}} - \tilde{v}_{ij}^{\text{exp}})^2}{(\tilde{u}_{ij}^{\text{th}})^2 + (\tilde{v}_{ij}^{\text{th}})^2}}. \quad (\text{S115})$$

For minimization, we use the MATLAB function *fminsearch* and obtain $\tilde{u}_{\text{EOF}} = 27.2 \mu\text{m/s}$ for the cylindrical object, and $\tilde{u}_{\text{EOF}} = 26.3 \mu\text{m/s}$ for the flower-shaped object. Figure S6 shows the experimental and theoretical flow fields for a cylindrical and a flower-shaped object as a result of the fitting procedure.

S.4.4.2. Determination of experimental cloaking and shielding conditions

After activating the gate electrode and applying the electric field, we perform a series of experiments with pressure-driven flow velocities in the range of 0–60 $\mu\text{m/s}$. Figures S7(a-g) and S8(a-g) show the experimental velocity field and corresponding streamlines for different pressure-driven velocities for the case of the cylindrical and the flower-shaped object, respectively. To determine which of the tested pressure-driven velocities corresponds to the cloaking or shielding conditions, we compute the deviation between the experimental and the theoretical flow fields. We use the theoretical flow field with the experimentally obtained velocity \tilde{u}_{EOF} (see S4.4.1) and its corresponding pressure-driven velocity \tilde{u}_{ext} that satisfies either the cloaking (S88) or the shielding (S97) condition. For the cylindrical object, we obtain $\tilde{u}_{\text{ext}} = 10.2 \mu\text{m/s}$ for shielding and $\tilde{u}_{\text{ext}} = 51.0 \mu\text{m/s}$ for cloaking. For the flower-shaped object, we obtain $\tilde{u}_{\text{ext}} = 9.86 \mu\text{m/s}$ for shielding and $\tilde{u}_{\text{ext}} = 49.3 \mu\text{m/s}$ for cloaking. Similar to the EOF velocity fitting, we use the function F_{fit} , given in (S114), to calculate the deviation between the theoretical velocity field and the experimental ones.

Figures S7(h) and S8(h) show the plots of the non-dimensionalized version of F_{fit} as a function of the external flow velocity for determination of experimental cloaking and shielding for the cases of the cylindrical and the

FIG. S7. (a)–(g) Experimental velocity field (blue arrows) and corresponding streamlines (black lines) around a cylindrical object for various external flow velocities and a fixed EOF velocity. The vector field is obtained from a PIV analysis, and the streamlines are plotted using the MATLAB function *streamline*. (h) Plot of the normalized version of F_{fit} as a function of the external flow velocity for determination of experimental cloaking (red crosses) and shielding (black crosses).

FIG. S8. (a)–(g) Experimental velocity field (blue arrows) and corresponding streamlines (black lines) around a flower-shaped object for various external flow velocities and a fixed EOF velocity. The vector field is obtained from a PIV analysis, and the streamlines are plotted using the MATLAB function *streamline*. (h) Plot of the normalized version of F_{fit} as a function of the external flow velocity for determination of experimental cloaking (red crosses) and shielding (black crosses).

flower-shaped object. For the cylindrical object, the minimum deviation between experiments and theory is obtained when $\tilde{u}_{\text{ext}} = 9.33 \mu\text{m/s}$ for shielding, and $\tilde{u}_{\text{ext}} = 53.8 \mu\text{m/s}$ for cloaking. For the flower-shaped object, the minimum deviation between experiments and theory is obtained when $\tilde{u}_{\text{ext}} = 10.0 \mu\text{m/s}$ for shielding, and $\tilde{u}_{\text{ext}} = 48.1 \mu\text{m/s}$ for cloaking. These values are in good agreement with the theoretically predicted pressure-driven velocities corresponding to cloaking and shielding conditions.

S.4.4.3. PIV analysis

To obtain the velocity field in the regions around the object, we use the open-source particle image velocimetry (PIV) software PIVlab [14]. For each experiment, we obtain the velocity field by averaging over 100 frames, each frame analyzed with a resolution of 1000×850 pixels with a conversion factor of $1.61 \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$. In PIVlab, we use the direct Fourier transform correlation algorithm with two interrogation areas: first pass with 128 pixels, and second pass with 64 pixels.

S.5. ILLUSTRATION OF SHIELDING FOR OBJECTS WITH A SIGNIFICANT DEVIATION FROM A CYLINDRICAL SHAPE

FIG. S9. Demonstration of hydrodynamic shielding for the case of a butterfly-shaped object. (a,b) Theoretically predicted and numerically obtained pressure distribution and streamlines corresponding to hydrodynamic shielding conditions with $\tilde{u}_{\text{ext}} = 16.6 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$ and $\tilde{u}_{\text{EOF}} = 43.3 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$, satisfying (S97). (c) Experimentally observed flow field (blue arrows) and resulting streamlines (black lines) in the case of $\tilde{u}_{\text{ext}} = 14.5 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$ and $\tilde{u}_{\text{EOF}} = 43.3 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$, corresponding to the best fit to the theoretical shielding conditions. The butterfly-shaped object is given by (S116), and the shielding region (purple lines) is defined by (S117), with $\tilde{r}_a = 2\tilde{r}_0$ and $\beta = 0.576$.

In this section, we show that our theory holds well even for complex-shaped objects with significant geometrical deviations from a cylindrical shape. For illustration, we consider a butterfly-shaped object parametrized by

$$r_{\text{obj}} = 1 + \beta f(\theta) = 1 + (\beta/\chi) [\cos(\theta) - 3 \cos(2\theta) + 2 \cos(3\theta) - 2 \cos(4\theta) - 2 \cos(5\theta) - \cos(7\theta)], \quad (\text{S116})$$

where $\chi = 5.7595$ is a normalization factor, such that $\max(|f|) = 1$. Using (S105), the corresponding shape of the shielding region is

$$r_{\text{sh}} = r_a + \beta g(\theta) = r_a + \frac{\beta}{\chi} \left[\cos(\theta) - \frac{3}{r_a} \cos(2\theta) + \frac{2}{r_a^2} \cos(3\theta) - \frac{2}{r_a^3} \cos(4\theta) - \frac{2}{r_a^4} \cos(5\theta) - \frac{1}{r_a^6} \cos(7\theta) \right]. \quad (\text{S117})$$

Figure S9 presents a comparison of theoretical predictions, finite-element simulation results and experimental observations for the butterfly-shaped object, corresponding to hydrodynamic shielding conditions, with $r_a = 2$ and $\beta = 0.576$, showing good agreement. As can be inferred from Fig. S9, the domain perturbation method holds well even in this case, thus suggesting that our theory can be applied to objects that significantly deviate from a cylindrical shape.

S.6. SUPPLEMENTAL MOVIE 1

Cloaking and shielding mode. Experimental visualization of cloaking and shielding of a cylindrical object with a radius of $100 \mu\text{m}$ and a circular cloaking/shielding region with a radius of $200 \mu\text{m}$ using fluorescent $1\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ particles. The video shows the transition from the native (only pressure), through shielded, to cloaked conditions by modifying the pressure-driven velocity for a fixed gate potential. Each frame of the video was background subtracted and obtained by the superposition of 12 frames of the raw data time lapse.

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